

Geometric properties of a new subclass of harmonic functions defined by q -differential inequality

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Abstract

This paper introduces a novel subclass of q -harmonic functions in the open unit disk, defined via an inequality involving the q -derivative operator. The geometric properties of this class, particularly its close-to-convexity characteristics, are investigated. Main results include coefficient bounds, growth estimates, and a sufficient coefficient condition ensuring class membership. Additionally, the closure properties of this subclass under convolution and convex combination are examined, highlighting its structural stability. By incorporating q -calculus, this study extends existing results in harmonic function theory and provides new insights into the geometric behavior of these functions.

Keywords: q -calculus, q -harmonic functions, coefficient bounds, distortion, q -close-to-convexity

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1. Introduction

In the realm of harmonic functions, each function f belonging to the class \mathcal{SH}^0 can be represented in the form $f = u + \bar{v}$, where

$$u(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} u_s z^s, \quad v(z) = \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} v_s z^s. \quad (1.1)$$

Here, both u and v are analytic functions within the open unit disk $\mathbb{E} = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}$. When the condition $|v'(z)| < |u'(z)|$ holds throughout the disk \mathbb{E} , it follows that the function f is sense-preserving and locally univalent in this domain. Furthermore, it is crucial to highlight that if $v(z)$ is identically zero, the class \mathcal{SH}^0 simplifies to the class \mathcal{S} .

The subclasses \mathcal{K} and \mathcal{S}^* of \mathcal{S} are characterized by their mappings of the unit disk \mathbb{E} onto close-to-convex and starlike domains, respectively. In a similar vein, the subclasses of \mathcal{SH}^0 that map the unit disk \mathbb{E} onto corresponding domains are denoted by $\mathcal{SH}^{0,*}$ and \mathcal{KH}^0 . For a more comprehensive understanding, one can refer to the detailed discussion in [5, 16].

Jackson's q -derivative for a function $u \in \mathcal{S}$, where $0 < q < 1$, is defined as follows [13]:

$$D_q u(z) = \begin{cases} \frac{u(z) - u(qz)}{(1-q)z}, & \text{if } z \neq 0, \\ u'(0), & \text{if } z = 0. \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

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It is important to note that if the function u is differentiable at z , then the limit as q approaches 1 from the left satisfies $\lim_{q \rightarrow 1^-} D_q u(z) = u'(z)$. In the context of equation (1.1), this q -derivative can be expressed as:

$$D_q u(z) = 1 + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q u_s z^{s-1}, \tag{1.3}$$

where the q -number $[s]_q$ is given by $[s]_q = \frac{1-q^s}{1-q}$ for any positive integer s . As q tends to 1 from the left, it is evident that $[s]_q \rightarrow s$.

Furthermore, Jackson defined the q -integral as follows [14]:

$$\int_0^z u(\zeta) d_q \zeta = z(1-q) \sum_{s=0}^{\infty} q^s u(zq^s), \tag{1.4}$$

provided that the series on the right-hand side converges. This definition plays a significant role in the study of q -calculus, particularly in examining the properties of functions within the class \mathcal{S} under q -differentiation and q -integration.

For more information on fractional derivatives, refer to the relevant literature [4, 15, 18].

A function $u \in \mathcal{S}$ is termed q -starlike in the open unit disk \mathbb{E} , and this is denoted by $u \in \mathcal{S}^*(q)$, if it satisfies the condition:

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{z D_q u(z)}{u(z)} \right\} > 0,$$

where D_q represents the Jackson q -derivative. Similarly, a function $u \in \mathcal{S}$ is called q -convex in \mathbb{E} , denoted by $u \in \mathcal{C}(q)$, if it fulfills the condition:

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{D_q(z D_q u(z))}{D_q u(z)} \right\} > 0.$$

Moreover, if there exists a q -convex function ϕ in \mathbb{E} , denoted by $u \in \mathcal{K}(q)$, such that

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{D_q u(z)}{D_q \phi(z)} \right\} > 0,$$

where $\mathcal{K}(q)$ represents the class of q -close-to-convex functions, then, in the particular case where $\phi(z) = z$, it follows that

$$\operatorname{Re}\{D_q u(z)\} > 0.$$

This definition generalizes the classical concepts of convex and starlike functions within the framework of q -calculus, offering a basis for examining these properties using Jackson’s q -derivative.

Ahuja and Çetinkaya [1] introduced the class of q -harmonic, univalent, and sense-preserving functions $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ in 2019, denoted as \mathcal{SH}_q^0 . A function \tilde{f} belongs to \mathcal{SH}_q^0 if and only if the condition

$$|\omega_q(z)| = \left| \frac{D_q v(z)}{D_q u(z)} \right| < 1$$

holds. Moreover, in the limiting case as $q \rightarrow 1^-$, the class \mathcal{SH}^0 is recovered. For additional discussions, refer to [2, 3, 20].

Using the Jackson q -derivative to build a new class of harmonic functions, we expand on these investigations.

Definition 1.1. The class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is defined as the set of functions $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{SH}_q^0$ that satisfy the inequality:

$$\operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} > |D_q v(z)| \quad \text{for all } z \in \mathbb{E}. \tag{1.5}$$

It is evident that the class P_H^0 , as studied by Ponnusamy et al. [17], is recovered in the limit as q approaches 1 from the left. For further details on harmonic function classes defined by differential inequality, see [6]-[10], [21].

Definition 1.2. The class $\mathcal{P}(q)$ consists of functions $u \in \mathcal{S}$ that satisfy the inequality:

$$\operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{E}). \tag{1.6}$$

These definitions extend the concept of harmonic functions in \mathcal{SH}^0 to those involving Jackson’s q -derivative, offering new insights and generalizations in the study of harmonic mappings.

Our investigation into the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$, defined through the q -differential operator in harmonic functions, forms the core of our study. In the subsequent sections, we delve into its intricate details, revealing its close-to-convex nature and uncovering fundamental properties such as coefficient conditions and growth estimates. Moreover, we explore its stability under convolution and convex combination, bolstering our understanding of its structural coherence. To foster a deeper comprehension of its geometric implications, we supplement our theoretical discourse with illustrative examples.

2. Geometric properties of the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$

In this section, we embark on an in-depth exploration of the intricate properties characterizing functions within the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. Our investigation spans across various dimensions, encompassing crucial aspects such as coefficient bounds, q -close-to-convexity, and growth estimates. Through meticulous analysis, we unravel the underlying mechanisms that define the behavior of these functions, shedding light on their intrinsic characteristics and geometric implications.

A function $f : \mathbb{E} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is called close-to-convex if it is univalent in the unit disk \mathbb{E} and its image $f(\mathbb{E})$ forms a close-to-convex domain. Specifically, a function f is said to be a q -close-to-convex harmonic function if it satisfies both the close-to-convexity condition and the q -harmonic property. One method for verifying the close-to-convexity of harmonic mappings is to analyze their connection with analytic functions. In this regard, Clunie and Sheil-Small established a valuable criterion in their study [5].

Lemma 2.1. *Suppose that $|D_q v(0)| < |D_q u'(0)|$. Let u and v be analytic functions in \mathbb{E} . With $|\varepsilon| = 1$ for each ε , $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v$ is close-to-convex, then $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ is also close-to-convex in \mathbb{E} .*

The following result establishes a connection between analytic functions in the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$ and functions belonging to $\mathcal{PH}(q)$.

Theorem 2.2. *The harmonic mapping $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$ if and only if $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v \in \mathcal{P}(q)$ with $|\varepsilon| = 1$ for each ε .*

Proof. Suppose that $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$, and for every complex number ε with $|\varepsilon| = 1$, let $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v$. Then, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Re} \{D_q \tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z)\} &= \operatorname{Re} \{D_q (u(z) + \varepsilon v(z))\} \\ &= \operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z) + \varepsilon D_q v(z)\} \\ &= \operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} + \operatorname{Re} \{\varepsilon D_q v(z)\} \\ &\geq \operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} - |\varepsilon D_q v(z)| \\ &= \operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} - |D_q v(z)| \\ &> 0. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it follows that $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z)$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$. Conversely, if we assume that $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z) \in \mathcal{P}(q)$, then we have

$$\operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} > \operatorname{Re} \{-\varepsilon (D_q v(z))\} \quad (z \in \mathbb{E}).$$

By appropriately choosing ε such that $|\varepsilon| = 1$, we can conclude that

$$\operatorname{Re} \{D_q u(z)\} > |D_q v(z)| \quad (z \in \mathbb{E}).$$

Hence, $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. □

Theorem 2.3. Every function in the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is q -close-to-convex within the domain \mathbb{E} .

Proof. Let $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ be a function belonging to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. By its definition, \tilde{f} is q -harmonic, univalent, and sense-preserving. Since $\tilde{f} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$, Theorem 2.2 guarantees that $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v$ is a member of $\mathcal{P}(q)$. This implies that \tilde{f}_ε is q -close-to-convex. As q approaches 1 from the left, \tilde{f}_ε becomes close-to-convex in the classical sense. Hence, using Lemma 2.1, we deduce that $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ is close-to-convex. Consequently, we conclude that \tilde{f} is indeed q -close-to-convex in \mathbb{E} . \square

Theorem 2.4. Let $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. For $s \geq 2$, we have

$$|v_s| \leq \frac{1}{[s]_q}. \tag{2.1}$$

For the function $\tilde{f}(z) = z + \frac{1}{[s]_q} \bar{z}^s$, this bound is tight, and equality holds.

Proof. Assuming $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$, with the function $v(re^{i\theta})$ represented as a series, where $0 \leq \rho < 1$ and $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$, we have the following inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho^{s-1} [s]_q |v_s| &\leq \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} |D_q v(\rho e^{i\theta})| d\theta \\ &< \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \operatorname{Re}\{D_q u(\rho e^{i\theta})\} d\theta \\ &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \operatorname{Re} \left[1 + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q u_s \rho^{s-1} e^{i(s-1)\theta} \right] d\theta = 1. \end{aligned}$$

As ρ approaches 1 from below, the required bound is obtained. \square

Theorem 2.5. Let $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. Then, for $s \geq 2$, the following inequalities hold:

$$|u_s| + |v_s| \leq \frac{2}{[s]_q}. \tag{2.2}$$

Equality is achieved by the function $\tilde{f}(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{2}{[s]_q} z^s$.

Proof. Let us consider that $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. From Theorem 2.2, it follows that $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$ for every ε where $|\varepsilon| = 1$. Consequently, we obtain

$$\operatorname{Re}\{D_q(u(z) + \varepsilon v(z))\} > 0$$

for all $z \in \mathbb{E}$. As a result, in the unit disk \mathbb{E} , there exists an analytic function Φ with a positive real part that can be expressed in the form $\Phi(z) = 1 + \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \phi_s z^s$. This ensures that

$$D_q(u(z) + \varepsilon v(z)) = \Phi(z).$$

By comparing the coefficients of both sides, we derive

$$[s]_q(u_s + \varepsilon v_s) = \phi_{s-1} \quad \text{for } s \geq 2.$$

Given that the real part of $\Phi(z)$ is positive, we have $|\phi_s| \leq 2$ for $s \geq 1$. Furthermore, considering that ε with $|\varepsilon| = 1$ is arbitrary, we can rigorously establish that inequality (2.2) holds true. The function $\tilde{f}(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{2}{[s]_q} z^s$ serves as an example to demonstrate that all the stated inequalities are indeed tight and exact. \square

A sufficient criterion for a function to be a member of the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is now provided.

Theorem 2.6. Suppose $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ belongs to the class \mathcal{SH}_q^0 , where

$$\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q (|u_s| + |v_s|) \leq 1. \tag{2.3}$$

Then, \tilde{f} is a member of the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$.

Proof. Let us consider that $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v}$ is an element of the class \mathcal{SH}_q^0 . By making use of the given condition (2.3), we can write the following series of inequalities:

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Re}\{D_q u(z)\} &= \operatorname{Re}\left[1 + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q u_s z^{s-1}\right] \\ &> 1 - \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q |u_s| \\ &\geq \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q |v_s| \\ &> \left|\sum_{s=2}^{\infty} [s]_q v_s z^{s-1}\right| = |D_q v(z)|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, it follows that \tilde{f} is indeed a member of the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. This conclusion is drawn from the fact that the real part of the q -derivative of u is greater than the modulus of the q -derivative of v , satisfying the necessary condition for \tilde{f} to belong to $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. \square

Theorem 2.7. Let $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. Then

$$|z| + 2 \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{s-1} |z|^s}{[s]_q} \leq |\tilde{f}(z)| \leq |z| + 2 \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{|z|^s}{[s]_q}.$$

Equality is achieved by the function $\tilde{f}(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{2}{[s]_q} z^s$.

Proof. Let $\tilde{f} = u + \bar{v} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. Using Theorem 2.2, we have $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u + \varepsilon v \in \mathcal{P}(q)$ for each ε ($|\varepsilon| = 1$). By employing a similar method as in [12], we obtain

$$\frac{1 - |z|}{1 + |z|} \leq |D_q \tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z)| \leq \frac{1 + |z|}{1 - |z|} \quad (|z| < 1). \tag{2.4}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} |D_q \tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z)| &= |D_q u(z) + \varepsilon D_q v(z)| \\ &\leq 1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} |z|^s \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |D_q \tilde{f}_\varepsilon(z)| &= |D_q u(z) + \varepsilon D_q v(z)| \\ &\geq 1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (-1)^s |z|^s, \end{aligned}$$

specifically, we have

$$|D_q u(z)| + |D_q v(z)| \leq 1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} |z|^s$$

and

$$|D_q u(z)| - |D_q v(z)| \geq 1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (-1)^s |z|^s.$$

Denote the radial segment from 0 to z by Γ . We get,

$$\begin{aligned} |\tilde{f}(z)| &\leq \int_{\Gamma} (|D_q u(\zeta)| + |D_q v(\zeta)|) |d_q \zeta| \\ &\leq \int_0^{|z|} \left(1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} |\rho|^s \right) d_q \rho \\ &= |z| + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{|z|^{s+1}}{[s+1]_q} \\ &= |z| + 2 \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{|z|^s}{[s]_q} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |\tilde{f}(z)| &\geq \int_{\Gamma} (|D_q u(\zeta)| - |D_q v(\zeta)|) |d_q \zeta| \\ &\geq \int_0^{|z|} \left(1 + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} (-1)^s |\rho|^s \right) d_q \rho \\ &= |z| + 2 \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^s |z|^{s+1}}{[s+1]_q} \\ &= |z| + 2 \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{s-1} |z|^s}{[s]_q}. \end{aligned}$$

□

3. Exploring closure properties of the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$

In this section, we delve into the realm of closure properties exhibited by the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ concerning convolutions and convex combinations. Through systematic examination, we elucidate the resilience of this class under such transformative operations, unveiling essential insights into its structural integrity and mathematical coherence.

Theorem 3.1. *The class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is closed under convex combinations.*

Proof. Let us consider that $\tilde{f}_k = u_k + \overline{v_k}$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$, and suppose further that the sum $\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k = 1$ with each coefficient $0 \leq \varphi_k \leq 1$. The convex combination of the functions \tilde{f}_k for $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ can be expressed as:

$$\tilde{f}(z) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k \tilde{f}_k(z) = u(z) + \overline{v(z)},$$

where

$$u(z) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k u_k(z) \quad \text{and} \quad v(z) = \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k v_k(z).$$

Both u and v are analytic functions within the open unit disk \mathbb{E} , satisfying the initial conditions $u(0) = v(0) = D_q u(0) - 1 = D_q v(0) = 0$. Now, we consider the real part of the q -derivative of u :

$$\begin{aligned} \operatorname{Re}\{D_q u(z)\} &= \operatorname{Re}\left[\sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k D_q u_k(z)\right] \\ &> \sum_{k=1}^n \varphi_k |D_q v_k(z)| \\ &\geq |D_q v(z)|, \end{aligned}$$

showing that f belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. □

A sequence $\{a_s\}_{s=0}^\infty$ of non-negative real numbers is termed a *convex null sequence* if it satisfies the following two conditions:

- (i) The terms of the sequence approach zero as $s \rightarrow \infty$:

$$\lim_{s \rightarrow \infty} a_s = 0.$$

- (ii) The differences between consecutive terms satisfy the inequality:

$$a_0 - a_1 \geq a_1 - a_2 \geq a_2 - a_3 \geq \dots \geq a_{s-1} - a_s \geq \dots \geq 0.$$

Lemma 3.2 (cf. [11]). *If $\{a_s\}_{s=0}^\infty$ is a convex null sequence, the function*

$$A(z) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{s=1}^\infty a_s z^s$$

is analytic, and its real part remains positive within the open unit disk \mathbb{E} .

Lemma 3.3 (cf. [19]). *Let $\Phi(z)$ be an analytic function in the domain \mathbb{E} such that $\Phi(0) = 1$ and $\operatorname{Re}\{\Phi(z)\} > 1/2$ for all $z \in \mathbb{E}$. Then, for any analytic function F defined in \mathbb{E} , the function $\Phi * F$ maps the image of \mathbb{E} under F to values within the convex hull of the image.*

Lemma 3.4. *Let $F \in \mathcal{P}(q)$, then $\operatorname{Re}\left[\frac{F(z)}{z}\right] > \frac{1}{2}$.*

Proof. Consider F belonging to the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$, defined as $F(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^\infty U_s z^s$. Then, the inequality

$$\operatorname{Re}\left[1 + \sum_{s=2}^\infty [s]_q U_s z^{s-1}\right] > 0 \quad (z \in \mathbb{E}),$$

can be equivalently expressed as $\operatorname{Re}\{\Phi(z)\} > \frac{1}{2}$ within the open unit disk \mathbb{E} , where

$$\Phi(z) = 1 + \frac{1}{2} \sum_{s=2}^\infty [s]_q U_s z^{s-1}.$$

Let $\{a_s\}_{s=0}^\infty$ be a sequence defined by

$$a_0 = 2 \text{ and } a_{s-1} = \frac{2}{[s]_q} \text{ for } s \geq 2.$$

It is clear that the sequence $\{a_s\}_{s=0}^\infty$ constitutes a convex null sequence. Utilizing Lemma 3.2, we deduce that the function

$$A(z) = 1 + \sum_{s=2}^\infty \frac{2}{[s]_q} z^{s-1}$$

is analytic, with $\operatorname{Re}\{A(z)\} > 0$ within \mathbb{E} . Expressing

$$\frac{F(z)}{z} = \Phi(z) * \left(1 + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \frac{2}{[s]_q} z^{s-1} \right),$$

and using Lemma 3.3, we arrive at the conclusion that $\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{F(z)}{z} \right\} > \frac{1}{2}$ for $z \in \mathbb{E}$. □

Lemma 3.5. *Let $u_m \in \mathcal{P}(q)$ for $m = 1, 2$. Then $u_1 * u_2 \in \mathcal{P}(q)$.*

Proof. Let $u_1(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \mathfrak{U}_s z^s$ and $u_2(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \mathfrak{B}_s z^s$, and

$$U(z) = (u_1 * u_2)(z) = z + \sum_{s=2}^{\infty} \mathfrak{U}_s \mathfrak{B}_s z^s.$$

Considering

$$D_q U(z) = D_q u_1(z) * \frac{u_2(z)}{z}. \tag{3.1}$$

Since $u_1 \in \mathcal{P}(q)$, we get $\operatorname{Re} [D_q u_1(z)] > 0$ ($z \in \mathbb{E}$). Moreover, using Lemma 3.4, $\operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{u_2(z)}{z} \right] > \frac{1}{2}$ in \mathbb{E} . Now, $\operatorname{Re} [D_q U(z)] > 0$ in \mathbb{E} results from applying Lemma 3.4 to (3.1). Thus, $U = u_1 * u_2 \in \mathcal{P}(q)$. □

Using Lemma 3.5, we now show that the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is closed under convolutions of its members.

Theorem 3.6. *For $m = 1, 2$, let $\tilde{f}_m \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$. Then, the convolution $\tilde{f}_1 * \tilde{f}_2$ also belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$.*

Proof. Assume that $\tilde{f}_m = u_m + \overline{v_m} \in \mathcal{PH}(q)$ for $m = 1, 2$. The convolution $\tilde{f}_1 * \tilde{f}_2 = u_1 * u_2 + \overline{v_1 * v_2}$ is defined as the convolution of the individual components of \tilde{f}_1 and \tilde{f}_2 . To demonstrate that $\tilde{f}_1 * \tilde{f}_2$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$, we need to show that the function $\tilde{f}_\varepsilon = u_1 * u_2 + \varepsilon(v_1 * v_2)$ belongs to $\mathcal{P}(q)$ for every ε with $|\varepsilon| = 1$.

According to Lemma 3.5, the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$ is closed under convolutions. For each ε with $|\varepsilon| = 1$, since $u_m + \varepsilon v_m \in \mathcal{P}(q)$ for $m = 1, 2$, we can assert that $\mathcal{P}(q)$ includes both U_1 and U_2 , where

$$U_1 = (u_1 - v_1) * (u_2 - \varepsilon v_2) \quad \text{and} \quad U_2 = (u_1 + v_1) * (u_2 + \varepsilon v_2).$$

Given that $\mathcal{P}(q)$ is closed under convex combinations, we can form the function

$$U_\varepsilon = \frac{1}{2}(U_1 + U_2) = u_1 * u_2 + \varepsilon(v_1 * v_2).$$

This function U_ε also belongs to the class $\mathcal{P}(q)$. Therefore, we can conclude that the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ is closed under convolution operations, meaning that the convolution of any two functions within $\mathcal{PH}(q)$ also remains within $\mathcal{PH}(q)$. □

4. Examples of functions in the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$

In this section, we provide several illustrative examples to demonstrate the applicability and geometric behavior of functions belonging to the class $\mathcal{PH}(q)$.

Example 4.1. Let $\tilde{f}(z) = z + 0.19z^5$. According to Theorem 2.6, the function $\tilde{f}(z)$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(\frac{1}{2})$. This function maps the unit disk to a starlike region, thereby making it close-to-convex. Figure 1 illustrates the image of concentric circles inside the unit disk \mathbb{E} under the transformation defined by $\tilde{f}(z) = z + 0.19z^5$.

Figure 1. The transformation $f(z) = z + 0.19z^5$ maps concentric circles within the unit disk to their corresponding images

Example 4.2. Let $g(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$. According to Theorem 2.6, the function $g(z)$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(\frac{1}{2})$. This function maps the unit disk to a close-to-convex region. Figure 2 illustrates the image of concentric circles inside the unit disk \mathbb{E} under the transformation defined by $g(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$.

Figure 2. The transformation $g(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$ maps concentric circles within the unit disk to their corresponding images

Example 4.3. Let $h(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$. According to Theorem 2.6, the function $h(z)$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(\frac{1}{2})$. This function maps the unit disk to a close-to-convex region. Figure 3 illustrates the image of concentric circles inside the unit disk \mathbb{E} under the transformation defined by $h(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$.

Figure 3. The transformation $h(z) = z + 0.20z^3 + 0.12z^5$ maps concentric circles within the unit disk to their corresponding images

Example 4.4. Let $\mathfrak{f}(z) = \mathfrak{f}(z) * \mathfrak{g}(z) = z + 0.0228z^5$, where \mathfrak{f} and \mathfrak{g} are the functions given in Example 4.1 and Example 4.2. According to Theorem 2.6, the function $\mathfrak{f}(z)$ belongs to the class $\mathcal{PH}(\frac{1}{2})$. This function maps the unit disk to a close-to-convex region. Figure 4 illustrates the image of concentric circles inside the unit disk \mathbb{E} under the transformation defined by $\mathfrak{f}(z) = z + 0.0228z^5$.

Figure 4. The transformation $\mathfrak{f}(z) = z + 0.0228z^5$ maps concentric circles within the unit disk to their corresponding images

5. Conclusion

In this study, we have introduced a new subclass of harmonic functions using Jackson's q -derivative operator. We have derived sufficient coefficient conditions for a harmonic function to belong to this subclass and identified distortion

classes for functions within it. Furthermore, we have demonstrated that the subclass is closed under convolution. The examples provided a better understanding of the results obtained. These findings are expected to contribute significantly to the field of geometric function theory.

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References

- [1] O. P. Ahuja and A. Çetinkaya, *Use of quantum calculus approach in mathematical sciences and its role in geometric function theory*, AIP Conf. Proc. **2095** (1), 2019; <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5097511>.
- [2] O. P. Ahuja and A. Çetinkaya, *Connecting quantum calculus and harmonic starlike functions*, Filomat **34** (5), 1431–1441, 2020; <https://doi.org/10.2298/FIL2005431A>.
- [3] O. P. Ahuja, A. Çetinkaya and Y. Polatoglu, *Harmonic univalent convex functions using a quantum calculus approach*, Acta Univ. Apulensis **58**, 67–81, 2019; <https://doi.org/10.17114/j.aua.2019.58.06>.
- [4] H. Bayram, *q-analogue of a new subclass of harmonic univalent functions associated with subordination*, Symmetry **14** (4), 2022; Article ID: 708, <https://doi.org/10.3390/sym14040708>.
- [5] J. Clunie and T. Sheil-Small, *Harmonic univalent functions*, Ann. Fenn. Math. **9** (1), 3–25, 1984; <https://doi.org/10.5186/aasfm.1984.0905>.
- [6] S. Çakmak, *Regarding a novel subclass of harmonic multivalent functions defined by higher-order differential inequality*, Iran J. Sci. **48**, 1541–1550, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40995-024-01697-7>.
- [7] S. Çakmak, *On properties of q-close-to-convex harmonic functions of order α* , Turk. J. Math. Comput. Sci. **16** (2), 471–480, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.47000/tjmcs.1507142>.
- [8] S. Çakmak, E. Yaşar and S. Yalçın, *New subclass of the class of close-to-convex harmonic mappings defined by a third-order differential inequality*, Hacet. J. Math. Stat. **51** (1), 172–186, 2022; <https://doi.org/10.15672/hujms.922981>.
- [9] S. Çakmak, E. Yaşar and S. Yalçın, *Some basic geometric properties of a subclass of harmonic mappings*, Bol. Soc. Mat. Mex. **28** (2), 2022; Article ID: 54, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40590-022-00448-1>.
- [10] S. Çakmak, E. Yaşar and S. Yalçın, *Some basic properties of a subclass of close-to-convex harmonic mappings*, TWMS J. Pure Appl. Math. **15** (2), 163–173, 2024; <https://doi.org/10.30546/2219-1259.15.2.2024.01163>.
- [11] L. Fejér, *Über die Positivität von Summen, die nach trigonometrischen oder Legendreschen Funktionen fortschreiten*, Acta Litt. Sci. Szeged. **1**, 75–86, 1925.
- [12] A. W. Goodman, *Univalent functions*, (Volume I), Mariner Publishing Co., Inc., 1983.
- [13] F. H. Jackson, *On q-functions and a certain difference operator*, Trans. R. Soc. Edinb. **46** (2), 253–281, 1909; <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0080456800002751>.
- [14] F. H. Jackson, T. Fukuda and O. Dunn, *On q-definite integrals*, Quart. J. Pure Appl. Math. **41**, 193–203, 1910.
- [15] O. Mishra and S. Porwal, *q-analogue of a class of harmonic functions*, Bol. Soc. Paran. Mat. **41**, 1–10, 2023; <https://doi.org/10.5269/bspm.52954>.
- [16] S. Owa, M. Nunokawa, H. Saitoh and H. M. Srivastava, *Close-to-convexity, starlikeness, and convexity of certain analytic functions*, Appl. Math. Lett. **15** (1), 63–69, 2002; [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0893-9659\(01\)00094-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0893-9659(01)00094-5).
- [17] S. Ponnusamy, H. Yamamoto and H. Yanagihara, *Variability regions for certain families of harmonic univalent mappings*, Complex Var. Elliptic Equ. **58** (1), 23–34, 2013; <https://doi.org/10.1080/17476933.2010.551200>.
- [18] S. Porwal, *q-analogue of a new subclass of harmonic univalent functions defined by fractional calculus operator*, Math. Sci. Appl. E-Notes **9** (2), 42–52, 2021.
- [19] R. Singh and S. Singh, *Convolution properties of a class of starlike functions*, Proc. Am. Math. Soc. **106**, 145–152, 1989; <https://doi.org/10.1090/S0002-9939-1989-0994388-6>.
- [20] S. Yalçın and H. Bayram, *On harmonic univalent functions involving q-Poisson distribution series*, Muthanna J. Pure Sci. **8** (2), 105–111, 2021; <https://doi.org/10.52113/2/08.02.2021/105-111>.
- [21] E. Yaşar and S. Yalçın, *Close-to-convexity of a class of harmonic mappings defined by a third-order differential inequality*, Turkish J. Math. **45** (2), 678–694, 2021; <https://doi.org/10.3906/mat-2004-50>.

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